

MANAGEMENT SYSTEM OF SPORTS FEDERATIONS AND ASSOCIATIONS

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***Abstract.** The study of the management system for physical education and sports, the impartiality reflected in statistics, and the delayed arrival of regulatory documents related to this sector, especially in a world rapidly evolving with innovative technologies, have resulted in an overwhelming amount of information for leaders. It was noted that decision-making in this context, especially with regard to promoting public health, is becoming increasingly complex.*

***Keywords:** executing actions, management, legislative framework, communication channels, information transition.*

The essence of management can be summarized as follows:

Gathering information about the physical condition of the population and the surrounding environment;

Processing and distributing this information through communication channels;

Using the processed information to form management directives;

Implementing these directives by transmitting the information to the appropriate executive bodies;

Executing actions and ensuring proper oversight.

It should be noted that in order to develop management decisions that achieve set goals, it is essential to have accurate information about both the external environment and the object of management. This information transfer mechanism is referred to as the “feedback loop.”

Various researchers have considered management systems both as processes and as management entities, which are not strictly distinct concepts, as processes themselves can be seen as part of the management system. At the leadership level, this has a structural nature, while at the level of teachers and coaches, it directly involves the management of training processes. Hence, it can be evaluated as the combination of the management object and the management system.

The organization and functioning of sports federations and associations is a key principle in building a democratic society. During the years of independence, Uzbekistan established a legislative framework regulating the activities of these sports federations and associations, in line with international democratic standards. This framework ensures the full implementation of the right to association. Sports federations and associations in Uzbekistan are non-governmental and non-commercial organizations.

A non-governmental, non-profit organization is established voluntarily by individuals and/or legal entities. Its primary goal is not to generate income (profit), and any income received is not distributed among its members. It is a self-governing entity.

A sports federation (association) is a membership-based organization that promotes and develops one or more sports, organizes competitions, and prepares athletes for national sports teams of Uzbekistan. It is a state-registered, non-governmental, non-profit organization. These federations may be international (world and regional) or national entities within the fields of physical culture and sports.

The primary functions of a sports federation are:

Organizing competitions and, when necessary, engaging sponsors. If an external party wishes to organize a competition, they must collaborate with the federation.

Publishing an official competition calendar.

Developing rules for the sport, including game regulations, equipment standards, and competition procedures.

Training and certifying sports officials.

Promoting sports activities.

Typically, a sports federation is responsible for one or more closely related sports. For example, FIFA oversees both soccer and futsal. Some organizations, such as the International Olympic Committee (IOC), manage multiple sports. In certain cases, multiple federations govern the same sport, necessitating distinctions such as “WBO World Boxing Champion” or “AMF Futsal.” Federations are often hierarchical, with national federations reporting to regional or international bodies. For example, the Football Federation of Uzbekistan is a member of the Union of European Football Associations (UEFA), which in turn is subordinate to FIFA.

Athletes range from amateur to elite international competitors, and federations may oversee professional, elite, or amateur sports. For example, the rules of professional American hockey (as governed by the National Hockey League) differ slightly from those of international hockey (as overseen by the International Hockey Federation).

Sports federations, whether global, regional, or national, are non-governmental, non-profit organizations operating within the domain of physical education and sports. In the Soviet Union, the first public sports associations (sections) emerged between 1923 and 1924 for sports like tennis, shooting, and chess. By the 1930s and 1950s, All-Union Sections were established for most sports developed in the country, eventually transitioning into sports federations by 1959.

The first international sports federation was established in 1881 for gymnastics. The largest sports federation in the world is the International Football Federation (FIFA).

In Uzbekistan, the Ministry of Youth Policy and Sports supports the activities of the National Olympic Committee, the National Paralympic Committee, various sports federations and associations, and other non-governmental non-profit organizations involved in physical education and sports.

A non-governmental, non-profit organization exists to protect the rights and legal interests of individuals and legal entities, promote democratic values, pursue social, cultural, and educational goals, meet spiritual and other non-material needs, conduct charitable activities, and pursue other socially beneficial objectives. The state ensures the protection of the rights and interests of these organizations and provides them with equal opportunities to participate in social life. Additionally, the government may support specific socially beneficial programs run by non-governmental organizations. Interference by state bodies and their officials in the activities of non-governmental organizations is prohibited.

Today, in economically developed countries, physical education and sports serve not only as a means to promote national health and international prestige but have also evolved into a profitable sector of the economy—the sports industry. The unpredictability of sports results adds to their appeal. Consequently, there is a growing need for advanced methods and models of sports management. Sports management now requires a constant search for solutions to both direct and indirect challenges in an unpredictable environment.

Presidential Decree No. PF-6099, dated October 30, 2020, “On Measures to Promote a Healthy Lifestyle and Further Develop Mass Sports,” has been adopted. The decree mandates that heads and employees of state bodies and organizations, as well as their family members, should participate in physical education and sports. It also calls for organizing competitions among these individuals, introducing workday fitness breaks, developing criteria to assess the health of employees (e.g., obesity levels and weight index), reducing the incidence of acute diseases, promoting public health, conducting analysis based on ratings, and ensuring online monitoring of results.

The modern sports industry is a dynamic and multifaceted entity, offering vast opportunities for implementing various initiatives, including entrepreneurial ventures. Intense competition for clients' time and money requires sports managers to think strategically, enabling them to objectively assess the complex, multi-factor market and social environment, set strategic goals, select appropriate strategies, and develop effective means for their implementation.

Today, economic processes and social relations are experiencing rapid, global shifts, driven by the information revolution. This has dramatically changed previous management perceptions and expanded its possibilities, introducing new opportunities, products, communication channels, and avenues for product distribution. Despite the fact that many management processes are now performed by computers, developing business ideologies, selecting directions, setting goals, and crafting strategies still rest firmly in human hands.

To navigate this evolving landscape, it is essential to create an innovative model that ensures the financial independence of sports organizations, particularly those related to the development of mass sports in Uzbekistan's regions. This involves creating the right conditions, establishing corporate management strategies based on the evaluation of physical education and sports development, devising innovative methodologies to meet the demand for young talented athletes, and creating an economic model that satisfies the demand for sports services. Scientifically substantiating the strategic concept of sports management is key to enhancing competitiveness in the global market, which necessitates the development of innovative methods.

The above information demonstrates the importance of enhancing the role of sports management to elevate sports in Uzbekistan to an industrial level. Implementing a sports management development model in physical education and sports is fundamental to addressing the sector's challenges comprehensively.

Physical education and sports are unique human services. Therefore, understanding “human capital” is crucial in the scientific foundation of sports management strategy development. This economic concept applies to various fields of human activity, but in physical education and sports, indicators such as the training level of coaches and athletes, their physical, mental, and social attributes, their experience in major competitions, and other factors play a vital role.

To address the challenges faced by sports organizations in Uzbekistan, forming a strategic management concept and an innovative mechanism for fully developing the services market in physical education and sports will allow us to solve several urgent issues:

- Making optimal management decisions in sports organizations;
- Strengthening brand recognition and market presence;
- Identifying independent sources of revenue;
- Enhancing the effectiveness of advertising efforts;
- Implementing customer-centric approaches;

Improving the image of sports organizations and producing competitive sports products for both domestic and foreign markets. This will create the necessary foundation for sports management strategies, encouraging cooperation between the public and private sectors, including coaches, athletes, referees, and other sports organization stakeholders. It will also involve fans, sponsors, and athletes in the buying and selling of sports services, while developing the economic foundations for the growth of mass sports, the sports business, a healthy lifestyle, and a system for coordinating and regulating sports activities.

An innovative model must ensure the financial independence of sports organizations engaged in developing mass sports in Uzbekistan's regions. It should create the appropriate conditions for their development, identify the demand for young, talented athletes, and establish an economic model that meets the demand for sports services. Additionally, a strategic concept for sports management based on scientific principles must be developed to ensure competitiveness in global markets. These are the functional tasks of sports managers.

The above approaches to sports management structure the sports industry based on organizational principles, following established institutions—such as school, student, professional, amateur, and recreational sports. This method helps define the social relations between sports entities and allows for a holistic view of the sports industry as a single system, making sports management strategies and tools more effective. Ultimately, this leads to a more in-depth and comprehensive understanding of sports management.

The most critical issue in management is making optimal decisions, which involves synthesizing various components of sports management. Among the many decisions made, management decisions—those involving the programming of physical education and sports organizations—are key. These decisions involve searching for and analyzing the necessary

information, setting goals and tasks, and ensuring their implementation. Management decisions are formalized in laws, decrees, orders, plans, and other documents, serving as products of the management process. As both a process and event, management decisions are characterized by the following steps:

The mechanism of factors influencing management decisions includes five steps:

- Understanding the problem;
- Searching for information;
- Comparing different alternatives;
- Making a purchase decision;
- Evaluating the purchase.

In practice, concepts such as integration, interdependence, sequence of steps, and the achievement of goals and objectives depend on the management strategy. From this perspective, the organization's strategy is an interconnected framework for developing decision-making rules, strengthening the organization's vitality and strength, and taking consistent steps to achieve goals and objectives based on the situation.

Thus, we have outlined the general concept of strategy. We have also reviewed the main types of strategy, their organizational levels, and their specific features. Next, we will consider the key principles of strategic management.

These strategic efforts are supported by the Public Fund for the Support of Non-Governmental Non-Profit Organizations, which operates under the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Established by a joint decision of the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis and the Senate Council in 2008, the fund aims to promote the growth of independent non-governmental non-profit organizations and other civil society institutions, ensuring their active participation in implementing democratic reforms in the country and promoting the liberalization of society. One of the fund's main objectives is to provide financial support from the state budget and other sources to encourage the development of civil society institutions and facilitate their involvement in addressing pressing social, economic, and humanitarian issues.

The Fund performs the following tasks to fulfill its mandate:

Participates in the allocation of funds from the State budget to non-governmental non-commercial organizations (NGOs) and other civil society institutions;

Ensures that State budget funds are spent as intended and used effectively, while mobilizing material resources for the stable and sustainable development of NGOs and strengthening the role and influence of civil society institutions;

Develops and implements financing programs for promising, social, and general projects of NGOs and other civil society institutions, aimed at addressing specific socio-economic issues in the regions and increasing citizens' social engagement;

Provides financial support for projects and programs related to strengthening the material and technical base of civil society institutions and offering them legal, advisory, organizational, technical, and other forms of assistance;

Attracts grants from foreign NGOs and international organizations to address specific social and general projects and to stimulate the development of civil society institutions.

The public fund is required to publish an annual report and ensure the transparency of its activities and the use of its resources. It must also allow representatives of registration bodies to participate in events organized by the Fund. The Fund is obligated to submit a report on its

activities to the Accounts Chamber of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Parliamentary Commission on Fund Management, as well as to registration bodies, tax authorities, and statistical bodies, in accordance with the law.

The Fund's resources are generated from various sources, including allocations from the State budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan, voluntary contributions from legal and natural persons (both residents and non-residents of Uzbekistan), grants, and free funds from international organizations and financial institutions, as well as other legally permissible sources.

Fund resources are distributed directly to NGOs and other civil society institutions in the form of subsidies, grants, and social orders, based on their requests and in accordance with the decisions of the Parliamentary Commission.

In addition to individual NGOs, the following associations and organizations are also considered independent beneficiaries of funding:

The National Association of Non-Governmental Non-Profit Organizations;

The Civil Society Research Institute;

The National Association of Electronic Mass Media;

The Regional Policy Fund;

The Public Fund for Support and Development of Independent Print Mass Media and News Agencies;

The Environmental Movement of Uzbekistan.

The establishment, operation, reorganization, and dissolution of political parties, trade unions, religious organizations, and certain other non-governmental non-profit organizations are regulated by special laws. The provisions of this law apply in cases where certain aspects of NGO activities are not covered by special legislation. If an international agreement of the Republic of Uzbekistan stipulates provisions that differ from the country's laws regarding NGOs, the provisions of the international agreement will take precedence.

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Decrees and decisions of our President

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